

Abstract:

Sugary drinks and soda are popular worldwide and they are linked to higher risk of kidney diseases from acute kidney disease to end stage renal disease and many people don't know the harmful consequences of drinking soda. The purpose of this mini study was to look at soda drinking frequencies and to check how much awareness young adults have about the possible kidney risks. A short online survey was conducted and a total of 40 respondents of different age groups completed it. The survey included questions about how often they drink soda, why they drink soda and do they know the side effects of drinking sugary drinks and soda.

Results have shown the significant soda consumption, with over half of respondents drinking 6 to 10 servings weekly, primarily driven by taste preference. Most participants (about 77.5%) correctly identified links between soda and conditions like obesity and diabetes. But awareness of kidney-specific risks was notably lower at around 57.5%. Importantly, after learning about potential kidney impacts through this survey, two-thirds of participants expressed willingness to reduce their soda intake.

These findings highlight a gap between consumption behaviour and specific health knowledge. It also suggests that awareness on kidney health and soda intake could encourage people to make healthier drink choices.

Our small survey offers a first look at this issue. The information gathered here can be a starting point. It can help guide bigger, more detailed studies on what people eat and what they know about their health.

Introduction:

Soft drinks have become a normal part of daily life for many young people. These drinks are easily available, inexpensive, and often chosen for taste or energy. Because of this soda consumption has increased over the years, especially among teenagers and young adults. Most people enjoy these drinks without thinking about their health effects, many studies have shown that frequent intake of sugary and acidic beverages can lead to adverse health outcomes including obesity, type 2 diabetes, kidney problems and cardiovascular diseases. The kidneys play an important role in filtering waste, balancing fluids, and keeping the body healthy. When a person regularly consumes drinks that contain added sugars, caffeine, and phosphoric acid, the kidneys may experience extra stress. Overtime, this may increase the chances of having kidney stones and acute kidney disease which could lead to chronic kidney disease(CKD).

Despite these possible risks, public awareness remains low and often focuses on links between soda and weight gain, while its specific impact on the kidneys receives less attention. The lifestyle choices and dietary habits of the youth can have long-term consequences for their health.

A short online survey was conducted to collect basic information about drinking habits and investigating the soda consumption patterns and the level of awareness youth have regarding kidney health risks.

Through a cross-sectional survey, this research answer three key questions: How frequently do young adults consume soda? What is their level of knowledge about the connection between soda and kidney disease? And, having knowledge about this risk change their consumption behaviour? The aim is not to prove medical conclusions but to highlight patterns and identify gaps in awareness that can be addressed through education.

Methods:

This mini study was carried out using a short online survey. The survey was created on Google Forms and shared through different online platforms. The purpose was to collect basic information about soda drinking habits and awareness of kidney health.

A total of 40 participants completed the survey. Participants were aged 15 or above and all responses were collected voluntarily. No personal or identifying information was asked, and all answers remained anonymous. The survey included multiple-choice questions about how often the respondents drink soda, why they are inclined to drink soda, their water intake, and do they know the link between soda and kidney problems.

Once the responses were collected, the data was automatically organized by Google Forms. Simple percentages and charts were used to understand the patterns. Since this is a small-scale project, the analysis focused on basic trends. The information gathered was then summarized and presented in Results section.

Results:

A total of 40 respondents participated in the survey. The age distribution showed that 37.5% were above 25 years old, while 30% were between 15-17 years. The rest fell into the remaining age groups. In terms of gender, 57.5% identified as male, 35% as female, and 7.5% preferred not to state their gender.

Soda consumption was common among the participants. When asked about frequency, the responses covered a wide range, including daily use, 3-4 times a week, once a week, rarely, or never. In terms of quantity, 52.5% reported drinking around 6-10 servings per week, while 25% consumed only 1-2 servings. Taste was the most common reason for choosing soda, followed by habit and peer influence.

Awareness related to kidney health varied. About 45% of respondents said they were aware that soda could affect kidney function, while 37.5% were unsure and 17.5% were completely unaware. When asked about general health risks, most participants linked soda consumption to

obesity (77.5%) and diabetes (77.5%). A smaller number (57.5%) recognized the potential risk to kidney health.

Several respondents reported experiencing symptoms after consuming soda. The most common were fatigue (37.5%) and frequent urination (22.5%), while 40% reported no symptoms at all. For water intake, 47.5% of the participants drank 1-2 liters per day, and 17.5% consumed less than one liter.

When asked whether they would reduce soda intake after learning about kidney-related effects, 62.5% answered that they would consider it, with 27.5% saying they would "definitely" reduce their intake. Only 10% said they would not change their habits.

Discussion:

This mini survey showed that soda drinking is very common among young people, but their awareness of how it can affect kidneys is limited. Many respondents consumed soft drinks several times a week and chose them mainly for taste or habit. Although some participants knew about the risks related to obesity and diabetes, fewer were aware that regular soda intake can also put stress on the kidneys.

The results also suggest that some young people experience mild symptoms such as fatigue or frequent urination after drinking soda, while many do not notice any immediate effects. Even so, most respondents said they would consider reducing their intake if they understood the kidney-related risks more clearly.

Overall, this mini project highlights the need for more awareness about how sugary and acidic drinks can affect long-term kidney health. While the sample size was small, the findings give a simple picture of current habits and show that education and healthier choices could make a positive difference.

Conclusion:

The findings of this survey give a small but useful look into how young people think about soda and kidney health. The results showed that many participants drink soda regularly, often several times a week. This is not surprising because soft drinks are easily available and widely consumed, especially by teenagers and young adults. Taste and habit were the most common reasons for drinking soda, which suggests that many people choose these drinks without thinking much about their health effects.

Awareness of kidney-related risks was mixed. While some respondents understood that excess sugar and acidic drinks can harm the kidneys, a large number either did not know or were unsure. This suggests that kidney health is not commonly discussed compared to more familiar issues like obesity and diabetes, which most participants were aware of. This gap in awareness

could lead to long-term health problems if regular soda consumption continues without any understanding of its effects.

Some respondents also reported symptoms such as fatigue or frequent urination, which can occur with dehydration or high sugar intake. However, these are self-reported and cannot be taken as medical proof. Still, they show that soda may affect individuals differently, and some might already be noticing minor changes in how they feel.

Overall, the survey highlights that soda is a routine part of daily life for many young people, but their knowledge about kidney health is limited. This shows the importance of simple health education, even at the school or college level. Since most participants said they would reduce soda intake if they knew more about kidney effects, awareness campaigns could have a real impact. Although this study had a small sample size, it provides helpful insight and can be a starting point for larger studies in the future.

References:

Malik, V. S., & Hu, F. B. (2019). Sugar-Sweetened Beverages and Cardiometabolic Health: An Update of the Evidence. *Nutrients*, 11(8), 1840.

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6723421/>

Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health. (2021, October). Sugary drinks. The Nutrition Source. <https://www.hsph.harvard.edu/nutritionsource/healthy-drinks/sugary-drinks/>

Cheungpasitporn, W., Thongprayoon, C., O'Corragain, O. A., Edmonds, P. J., & Erickson, S. B. (2014). Associations of sugar-sweetened and artificially-sweetened soda with chronic kidney disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Nephrology (Carlton)*, 19(12), 791-797.

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